

COMPACTION RESPONSE OF FIBRE REINFORCEMENTS DEPENDING ON PROCESSING TEMPERATURE

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SUMMARY

The compaction behaviour of textile reinforcements in Liquid Composite Moulding has to be taken into consideration for the design and optimisation of closed mould manufacturing processes. Important processing and final product characteristics such as permeability and fibre volume fraction are affected by the deformation of the reinforcement during preforming and impregnation. In the present work a carbon fibre Non Crimp Fabric with an interlayer toughening fleece has been subjected to different preheating conditions and the influence on the compaction response has been analysed.

Keywords: Liquid Composite Moulding, Resin Transfer Moulding, compaction, preforming, fibre volume content.

INTRODUCTION

The compaction response of the fibre reinforcement is affecting both the manufacturing parameters and the mechanical properties of the final product [1]. In typical Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) processes the mould is assumed to be rigid and closed prior to injecting the resin, so no significant variation of the fibre volume content can be expected. Nevertheless a representation of the reinforcement stress state is required in order to predict the distribution of forces applied to the RTM mould and thus to optimize the dimensioning of the tooling.

In resin infusion processes under flexible tooling the flow problem is coupled to the deformation of the fibre reinforcement as far as its permeability is changing with the variation of the fibre volume fraction, which can be expressed as a function of the compaction pressure. A correct model for the deformation process is also necessary in order to predict the evolution of preform thickness during the infusion.

The behaviour of the reinforcement must be considered not only for the process itself but also in the preforming operations previous to the closed mould phase. As far as differences in the material response under different temperature treatments have been perceived, adequate stress-deformation models must be used depending on pre-processing and processing temperatures. This work focuses on preheating treatments for

impregnation processes carried out on not heated moulds. This would be the situation in the low-cost production of large structures, where a heated tooling would be too expensive and the process should be run at room temperature. Another case of interest would be processing with heated tooling without preforming.

The response of fibre reinforcements to transversal loading has been widely studied in literature. The most commonly used expression to model the compaction behaviour is the power law (Eq. 1) used by Robitaille *et al.* in [2-4].

$$\sigma = a \cdot V_f^k \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Where σ represents the transversal stress, V_f is the fibre volume fraction and a and k are material parameters. Adjusting a and k , the dry and wet behaviour can be described. Although this model fits well to experimental data, it presents a singularity when the applied compaction pressure is still zero, as it implies that the fibre volume content is zero and thus, the thickness of the laminate is infinite. It makes the implementation of these models in simulation a difficult task. A modified model was used by [5] to avoid this problem.

Van Wyk [6] studied the properties of wool and derived the power equation for the compaction of a 3D network of randomly oriented fibres. The physical model assumes that the fibres behave like bending beams that transmit loads through contact points. The compaction pressure increases with the 3rd power of the fibre volume content. One disadvantage of this early approach is that it is not able to handle with aligned fibres. Gutowski *et al.* [7] studied the consolidation of pre-impregnated reinforcements and proposed different versions of a compaction model for aligned and undulated fibres, where fibres are initially bent and straighten under pressure. In [8] Batch and co-workers measured compaction pressures of different sorts of reinforcements. They fitted their experimental data to a model where the fibre is modelled as a bulking arc contacting at two single points at the beginning of the compaction, increasing the contact region gradually as the compaction pressure increases. Fibre volume content is linearly related with compaction pressure at the beginning of the compaction but presents a nonlinear relation for higher values of pressure. Some other models have been proposed to describe the compression behaviour of fibrous reinforcement like the exponential fit of Kang [9].

None of the above mentioned models take effects like the permanent deformation remaining after compression, hysteresis or the effects of cyclic loading into account [10].

Bickerton [11] and Kelly [12] studied the time depending behaviour of fibre reinforcements modelling both the compression and relaxation phases by means of the same viscoelastic model. They showed the effect of compression rate on maximum stress required to reach the desired fibre volume content and the relaxation effect after loading. They used a viscoelastic model that performs well at the high levels of compaction reached in RTM processes.

More recently Bayldon [13] presented an interpolation model based on Gutowski's approach that tries to describe the compaction stages in typical flexible bag processes considering partial unloading and reloading cycles.

In [14] a new formulation considering stored and frictional dissipated energy has been presented.

The objective of this work is to explore the influence of the temperature history on the compaction and relaxation grade under compression in preforming and liquid composite moulding processes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Compaction experiments have been carried out in a universal testing machine using a 2.5 kN load cell. The dry samples have been set to transversal compaction between parallel plates. The lower plate remains fixed during the experiment while the upper one applies the load on material at constant velocity. The force required to reach this strain is recorded.

The samples have been prepared from square fresh cuts. The layers have been stapled keeping always the same orientation of the stitch (5x5 zigzag stitch) and bundles. Each sample consists of 8 tri-axial layers. The material is a 24 K carbon fibre multiaxial non-crimp fabric (+45°/0°/-45°) and has an areal weight of about 600 g/m². This textile has a PA-based toughening fleece between each uniaxial layer (approx. 7 gsm each layer) with a melting point about 170 °C.

The aim of this set of measurements is to determine the influence of a preheating treatment on the compressibility of the material in dry conditions. With this purpose some samples have been heated at 60°C and 120°C for 24 hours in an electric oven, while other coupons remained at room temperature for comparison. The compression test was carried out at room temperature.

The instantaneous fibre volume content V_f has been calculated as a geometric definition of the reinforcement package grade [8, 15], as expressed with Eq. 2:

$$V_f = \frac{n \cdot S}{\rho \cdot d} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where n is the number of layers which make up each stack, S is the areal weight of the reinforcement, ρ is the density of the fibres as a solid phase and d is the stack thickness, which is a function of the applied pressure.

As mentioned before, the textile has an initial fibre volume content already when no external load is applied, labelled V_{f0} . This initial fibre volume fraction is function of the sample thickness before compacting, which is not easy to measure. This starting thickness has been considered when a fixed very low level of pressure is applied.

In order to establish a relationship between applied force and deformation of the staples loading cycles have been applied at a velocity of 0.5 mm/min until a maximum load equivalent to 2 bar. Once this maximum load level has been reached, the deformation is held constant until relaxation of the material. To get knowledge about the permanent deformation and the viscoelastic behaviour of the reinforcement, repeated loading cycle tests have also been performed. To verify the repeatability of the process, replications of the experiments have been executed.

RESULTS

In Fig. 1 the evolution of the material thickness depending on compaction pressure at different preheating temperatures is shown. It can be seen that the increase of treatment temperature leads to a significant expansion in the material thickness. The mean values of initial thickness (H_0) can be observed in Table 1. According to Eq. 2, that leads to lower final volume fraction values, as can be seen in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Thickness of the samples depending on compaction pressure at different temperatures.

An evaluation of the initial thicknesses has shown a variation in the transversal geometry of the samples after the heat treatment. As it can be seen in Table 1, an increase of initial thickness and thus a reduction in the starting fibre volume content is to be expected when heating the samples. This effect suggests a reset in the history of the reinforcement that should affect the compaction characteristics of the material.

Table 1: Initial thicknesses H_0 at different pre-heating temperatures, initial fibre volume contents V_{f0} and final volume contents $V_{f,max}$ (mean values).

	RT	60 °C	120 °C
H_0	10.006	10.522	11.85
V_{f0}	0.281617	0.2679	0.23737
$V_{f,max}$	0.624264	0.60175	0.57872

Fig 2: Fibre volume content at room temperature (blue), 60 °C (green) and 120 °C (red), depending on compaction pressure.

In fact, the outcome is a reduction of the fibre volume content achievable for the same level of compaction pressure (Fig. 2) and that would have consequences on the processability (permeability) and quality of the final part when trying to accomplish requirements regarding laminate thickness and dimensional tolerances.

However, the evolution of the fibre volume content represents the absolute deformation of the material. In Fig. 3, the engineering strain depending on compaction pressure is depicted.

Fig 3: Strain depending on compaction pressure, at room temperature (blue), 60 °C (green) and 120 °C (red).

This strain is expressed as (Eq. 3)

$$\epsilon = \frac{H_0 - H}{H_0} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

with H_0 and H , initial and instantaneous thicknesses respectively. Although significant variation of the strain has already been detected preheating at 60°C , the relative deformation of the material is considerably higher at 120°C .

It has been mentioned before that the reinforcement which is subject of this study presents a toughening thermoplastic fleece between each UD carbon fibre layer. It has been observed, that this toughening system is undergoing a modification in its geometry when applying a similar heating treatment as for the NCF samples. The originally plane textile gets shrunk and increases its waviness after heating. The filaments, which were originally highly oriented try to recover their disordered state after being heated. This event would only be partially restricted by the stitching in the assembled multidirectional fabric. The change in the geometry of the toughening (presented in Fig. 4) would be a plausible explanation for the increase in the initial sample thickness mentioned earlier. The results obtained with similar non crimp fabrics without toughening, which show no difference between pre-heated and non heated probes are also suggesting this justification.

Figure 4: thermoplastic toughening fleece before heating (left) and after heating at 120°C (right). The corresponding microscopic images can be observed underneath.

As reported widely in previous research, compression behaviour is highly time dependant. In the following graph (Fig. 5) the compression pressure and relaxation of the material at the maximum pressure deformation are depicted.

Fig 5: Evolution of the compaction pressure throughout compaction and relaxation.

From the evaluation of these curves, it can be seen that the relaxation effect is significantly higher in the case of the pre-heated samples. A pressure decay of about 24% after the first compaction cycle for the ordinary prepared reinforcements has been observed. That reduction increases up to 28% and more than 37% for 60°C and 120°C respectively (Fig. 6).

Fig 7: Relaxation of the reinforcement: ratio *Relaxation Pressure/Maximum Pressure* at different heating treatments.

The remaining deformation after each loading/relaxation/unloading cycle has been characterised by means of repetitive cycles performed on the same sample. The preheated coupons were loaded and set to constant deformation until relaxation in a 4 runs recurrent experiment. As it can be seen, the thickness decreases with each loading

process (Fig. 8). This permanent deformation in the material is higher in the case of the heated samples, especially at 120°C. The increase in the fabric packing comes accompanied by a reduction in the material relaxation (Fig. 9). Nevertheless, it can be seen that the heated samples are following a parallel tendency, although at different levels.

Fig 8: Thickness after each loading cycle. The permanent deformation after repeated compaction/relaxation cycles can be observed.

Fig 9: Pressure decay during sequential loading cycles.

CONCLUSIONS

The deformation of the reinforcement during filling will affect the pressure field over the mould, and its prediction will help to optimise the processing and tooling design. The compaction behaviour has an influence on important characteristics of the material like permeability. In some variants of the process which use a flexible bag as one half of the mould the compaction response has a direct influence on the local permeability, the laminate thickness evolution and the final fibre volume content as well.

Different preforming and tooling circumstances can be presented in the manufacturing of large structures. Regarding to this, the thermal history of fabric reinforcement has an influence on the compressibility of the material and also on time dependent effects like relaxation after transversal loading. The resulting state of stress can influence the further residual stress distribution, i.e. during curing. The experimental results discussed here are opening new possibilities to aim-oriented preforming, where targeted fibre volume contents could be achieved through local heat treatments. Consequently, it deserves to be further experimentally investigated and mathematically described in order to get accurate and easy to implement simulation models.

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